

**METAPHORS AND THEIR FEATURES OF TRANSLATION BASED
ON THE MATERIAL OF THE WORKS OF J. K. ROWLING "HARRY
POTTER"**

Fayziyev Bahodir Baxshullayevich

A teacher of the Department
Of English Literature and
Translation studies
Bukhara State University
b.b.fayziyev@buxdu.uz
tel: +998 90 635 05 20

Abstract: Literary translation is one of the most difficult types of translation activity; this type of translation must be performed in such a way that the atmosphere of the plot and the author's style are fully preserved. The translator is faced with the task of making the text interesting while preserving the style, conveying the author's intentions, thoughts and feelings by transforming his images into material of another language.

Key words: translation, name, metaphorical, author, magical, transfer, heroine, image

Introduction

The most important thing is to accurately recreate the picture of the world laid down by the author in the work, since it is metaphorization that makes it possible to recreate such a picture of the world. Based on this, an adequate artistic translation of the metaphorical images of the original work becomes of great importance.

Metaphor is one of the most common forms of creating reality in fiction and, at the same time, the most difficult to translate. Therefore, it is quite justified that the features of the translation of metaphors have been and remain at the forefront of linguistic discourse.

Methods

The relevance of the topic of literary translation is also evidenced by the fact that it was dealt with by such outstanding linguists and translation experts as Y. Apresyan, I. Arnold, N. Arutyunova, L. Barkhudarov, A. Vezhbitskaya, V. Karaban, V. Komissarov, V. Telia, S. Ter-Minasova, A. Fedorov and others.

Metaphor translation is linked to the resolution of several linguistic, literary, cultural, philosophical, and other issues. The function of the metaphor in the text, stylistic considerations, the text's style, and the goal of the translation all play a role in the method of translating metaphors that is chosen. Cultural differences are sometimes noted as the fundamental issue with translating metaphors; some metaphors have different connections or are not very important. For instance, it is not always easy to simply transfer metaphors from one text to another since Russian frequently lacks the metaphorical imagery that are characteristic of the English language and vice versa. In this sense, it is necessary to alter the metaphorical image; doing so preserves the original's degree of expressiveness and improves the idiom in the translation.

For the theory and practice of translation, it is crucial to maintain the traditional separation between author's (creative, speaking, individual) and conventional (erased, linguistic) metaphors. Different approaches to translating a metaphor are taken depending on whether the person falls into the first or second category. It is advisable to translate original metaphors as closely as possible, however when translating ordinary metaphors, one should try to locate a frequently used equivalent in the target language.

The translation of traditional metaphors can be named in a variety of ways. The most widely used categorization is that of V.N. Komissarov, who makes a distinction between the following categories of traditional metaphor translation: The translations include: - a literal translation of the metaphor (as black as sin – black as sin); - a translation based on another similar image (broken English – broken English); - non-metaphorical explanations (as large as life – life-size). [2 p. 70].

When faced with an author's metaphor, most translators advocate fidelity to the author's text and recognize the possibility of maneuver when this is due to linguistic or artistic necessity. They try to see through the author's eyes and convey what they saw with carefully chosen means of their language; they are not content to drag all the original words into the translation without analysis or consideration of their functions in different languages. This presents problems when a translator tries to find a worthy equivalent to the author's metaphor.

Result

Regarding J. K. Rowling's Harry Potter novels, they are a goldmine of information for studying figurative language because the author purposefully employs a wide range of metaphors to paint a more vivid picture of the characters. Our primary focus will be on the metaphors used by the author.

Associative links between facts and real-world phenomena enable metaphor to make sense of new phenomena in a fantastical, nonexistent universe. New meanings for words that can have a nominative purpose can be derived from metaphor.

Metaphorical transfer can occur when there is a resemblance in terms of color, size, shape, attributes, and purposes. Metaphorization is based on specific cognitive principles. When an item of extralinguistic reality is categorized, it is always linked to both rational and emotional-evaluative associations; together, these associations create a particular conceptual model that is consistent with perceptions of the object within a particular language community.

For instance, in the Harry Potter book series, "The Bluebottle: A Broom for All the Family - safe, reliable, and with Built-in Anti-Burglar Buzzer..." is the name of one brand of magical transportation (a family-use broom). [13]. A brilliant blue-colored species of corpse fly is known by the name "bluebottle" [7]. The capacity for flight and color serve as the foundation for metaphorical transfer. This broom model is referred to as "Blue Fly" in the Russian language [5].

In the Harry Potter novel, the lexeme howler is used to nominate a magical object of the magical world: "“What's a Howler?” he said. Ron stretched out a shaking hand,

eased the envelope from Errol's beak, and slit it open. Neville stuffed his fingers in his ears. A split second later, Harry knew why." [9]. Howler is a letter in a red envelope that wizards send to each other with angry tirades. The peculiarity of this letter is that it reads out loud the message of the addressee. In English howler has the meaning of "howler" or "mourner" [8]. In Russian, this item is called "thundercaster" or "shouter" [1]. So, by means of metaphorical transfer in the name of an object in the magical world, the ability to talk or scream is conceptualized.

One of J. K. Rowling's characters, a special correspondent for the newspaper of the world of magicians "The Daily Prophet", has the surname SkeeterRita (Russian version - Rita Skeeter [4]). In English, the lexeme skeeter is used to denote a mosquito [7]. By giving the heroine such a surname, the writer emphasizes the character's ability for magical transformations. The heroine could easily turn into a beetle: "'No, you see ...Rita Skeeter' – Hermiones voice trembled with quiet triumph – 'is an unregistered Animagus. She can turn – 'Hermione pulled a small sealed glass jar out other bag. 'into a beetle' [10]. This surname clearly emphasizes such a character trait of the heroine as annoyingness, which is also a typical trait of a mosquito. Thus, by metaphorically transferring the external characteristics of the form and the internal form of the expression "the mosquito is annoying" - "the person is disturbing, annoying", certain character traits are conveyed.

Discussion

Black Sirius is the name of a representative of a family of sorcerers who professed hatred of everyone who does not have magical abilities and is of dubious origin. Sirius is one of the few who opposed established family values, for which he was punished: "Large word satt hevery top of the tapestry read: The Nobleand Most Ancient House of Black. 'You're not on here!' said Harry, after scanning the bottom of the tree closely. 'I used to be there,' said Sirius, pointing at a small, round, charred hole in the tapestry, rather like a cigarette burn. 'My sweet old mother blasted me off after I ran away from home.' [10]. The hero's name comes from the name of the brightest star - Sirius. By means of metaphorical transfer in a person's own name, the characteristic features of a

star are conceptualized - brightness and uniqueness. Note that the ancient Sumerian name for the star Sirius is “dog of the sun” [12]. From this name comes the name of the constellation Canis Major, where the star is located. Sirius Black [6] also had the magical ability to transform into a dog. Thus, the basis of metaphorical transfer is the shape of the constellation.

Thus, we see that some metaphors, primarily anthroponyms (Rita Skeeter, Sirius Black), were translated using transcription, which led to a loss of metaphor, due to which the meaning intended by the author was partially distorted. To convey the realities of the magical world into Russian, transliteration (Nimbus-2000), literal translation (Blue Fly) and translation based on the same image (thundercaster, chant) were also used. These techniques are classic translation techniques.

Conclusion

It is obvious that in each specific case the translator is not faced with the task of choosing from several ready-made options, but there is a need to creatively search for a way out of the situation with the least loss in terms of preserving the style and content of the original. When identifying a metaphor in the text, the translator must decide whether it should be reflected in the translation and how best to do this.

References

1. Комиссаров В. Н. Лингвистика перевода. М.: Международные отношения, 1980. 167 с.
2. Коломиец Л.А., Норец М.В. Особенности перевода авторского стиля Джоан Роулинг «Гарри Поттер и орден феникса» / Л.А. Коломиец, М.В. Норец // I научно-практической конференции "Переводческий дискурс: междисциплинарный подход" 27 - 29 апреля 2017 года, г. Симферополь. – С. 206-210.
3. Cambridge Dictionary online [Electronic Resource]. – Mode of access: URL: <http://dictionary.cambridge.org> (дата обращения 26.01.2020).

4. Online Etymology Dictionary [Electronic Resource]. – Mode of access: URL: <http://www.etymonline.com> (дата обращения 26.01.2020).

5. Rowling J. K. Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets [Electronic Resource] – Mode of access: URL: http://www.greylib.su/?category=englishengkids&altname=ves_harri_potter_na_an_gliiskom_all_harry_potter_books (дата обращения 26.01.2020).

6. Rowling J. K. Harry Potter and the Order of the Phoenix [Electronic Resource] – Mode of access: URL: http://www.greylib.su/?category=englishengkids&altname=ves_harri_potter_na_an_gliiskom_all_harry_potter_books (дата обращения 26.01.2020).

7. Rowling J. K. Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone [Electronic Resource] – Mode of access: URL: http://www.greylib.su/?category=englishengkids&altname=ves_harri_potter_na_ang_liiskom_all_harry_potter_books (дата обращения 26.01.2020).

8. Subject Dictionary Glossary Lexicon Thesaurus [Electronic Resource]. – Mode of access: URL: <http://www.ats-group.net/glossary-lexicon.html> (дата обращения 26.01.2020).

9. The Quidditch World Cup [Electronic Resource] – Mode of access: URL: <https://www.wattpad.com/688521966-black-dogs-the-quidditch-worldcup> (дата обращения 26.01.2020).